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COMPARISON OF THE REACTIVITY OF SOME ALDEHYDES AND ACIDS IN OXIDATION REACTIONS

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Annotation: The process of oxidation of methacrolein, acrolein, and acids in the presence of different catalysts has been investigated. It has been shown that, in the presence of these catalysts, saturated aldehydes are more easily oxidized compared to unsaturated aldehydes.

A proposed scheme of the process of methacrolein oxidation is offered. A comparison table of the oxidation rates of aldehydes, acetone, and acids is also provided.

Keywords: oxidation, methacrolein, acrolein, methacrylic acid, acetaldehyde, catalysts

СРАВНЕНИЕ РЕАКЦИОННОЙ СПОСОБНОСТИ НЕКОТОРЫХ АЛЬДЕГИДОВ И КИСЛОТ В РЕАКЦИЯХ ОКИСЛЕНИЯ

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Аннотация: Исследован процесс окисления метакролеина, акролеина и кислот в присутствии различных катализаторов. Показано, что в присутствии этих катализаторов насыщенные альдегиды окисляются легче, чем ненасыщенные.

Предложена предполагаемая схема процесса окисления метакролеина. Также приведена сравнительная таблица скоростей окисления альдегидов, ацетона и кислот.

Ключевые слова: окисление, метакролеин, акролеин, метакриловая кислота, ацетальдегид, катализаторы

Introduction: The study investigates the oxidation process of methacrolein and acrolein on different catalysts.

It has been established that, during the oxidation of methacrolein and acrolein on various catalysts, the main products are methacrylic acid, acrylic acid, acetic acid, CO₂, and CO. In addition, smaller amounts of formaldehyde (CH₂O), acetone, propionaldehyde, propionic acid, n-hexane, or n-hexanol are formed.

It is known that in catalysts with the same composition, the reactivity of homologous series compounds in oxidation reactions (especially if the oxidation reactions proceed through different rate-determining steps) is determined either by their structure or by the activation energy of the limiting stage. It is clear that in catalysts with different compositions, the relative reactivity can vary depending on the reaction mechanism.

Experiments have shown that in the gas phase, the selectivity of the oxidation of isobutylene to methacrylic acid in the presence of a Te-V-Mo-Cr-O contact is lower than the analogous oxidation of propylene. This is explained by differences in the reactivity of aldehydes and acids derived from these olefins.

In this regard, the oxidation of various saturated and unsaturated aldehydes and acids has been studied on Mo₁₂P₂CS_{1.8}Pb_{0.5}CrO_x catalysts.

Experimental part. The oxidation process of methacrolein, acrolein, methacrylic acid, acrylic acid, and propionic acid was investigated under identical conditions (contact time, gas flow rate, and fixed reaction temperature) [1-4].

Table 1 presents the reactivity of aldehydes and acids at temperatures between 530-610 K. For unsaturated aldehydes, at 560 K, the reactivity order was established as follows:

Methacrolein (MA) → Ethylacrolein (EA) → Propylacrolein (PA)
→ Acrolein (AKT)

Our research indicates that on $Mo_{0.75}V_{20}Te_{0.5}O_x$ catalysts, the oxidation rates of acrolein and methacrolein are nearly identical. However, the activation energy for methacrolein is higher. On these catalysts, acrolein exhibits higher reactivity than methacrolein.

The reactivity order of unsaturated aldehydes at 560 K is:

Methacrolein → Ethylacrolein → Propylacrolein → Acrolein

On $Mo_{0.12}P_2CS_{1.8}Pb_{0.5}CrO_x$ catalysts, at 590 K (the optimal temperature for the oxidation of methacrolein to methacrylic acid), the conversion rates of saturated and unsaturated aldehydes differ significantly [5-9]. The sequence of the conversion rates for saturated and unsaturated aldehydes is as follows:

Acetaldehyde → Propionaldehyde → n-Butyraldehyde → Isobutyraldehyde → Acetone

At the same conversion rate, the formation of unsaturated acids from unsaturated aldehydes follows the sequence:

Ethylacrolein → Propylacrolein → Methacrolein → Acrolein

Table 1 – Oxidation rates of aldehydes, acetone, and acids on $Mo_{0.12}P_2CS_{1.8}Pb_{0.5}CrO_x$ catalysts. Reagent ratio (m^3/m^3): R:Air:H₂O = 0.2:3:1

№	Oxidizing compounds	Oxidation products	Conversion rate of oxidation products at temperature T (K), ($w \cdot 10^{-2}$) mol/m ³ ·s			
			530	560	590	610
1	AKT	ST		4.8	12.6	22.5
		AK	1.65	2.25	4.8	8.1
		CO ₂	0.61	1.21	2.3	4.7
		CO	0.65 –	0.25	1.7	5.1
		Total	2.91	8.51	21.4	40.4
2	MA	ST	4.2	4.8	7.6	9.6

№	Oxidizing compounds	Oxidation products	Conversion rate of oxidation products at temperature T (K), ($w \cdot 10^{-2}$) mol/m ³ ·s			
			530	560	590	610
		MAT	8.5	10.5	14.6	22.3
		CO2	0.5	1.3	1.9	4.0
		CO	-	0.4	0.9	1.7
		Total	13.2	17.0	25.0	37.6
3	EA	ST	0.8	0.6	1.5	3.5
		EAK	6.7	14.5	23.1	40.4
		CO2	0.6	0.3	0.8	2.4
		CO	-	-	0.4	1.3
		Total	8.1	15.4	25.9	47.6
4	Acetone	ST	2.7	6.2	16.2	29.5
		CO2	0.7	1.4	2.9	6.2
		CO	-	0.3	1.6	6.7
		Total	3.4	7.9	20.7	42.4
5	Acetaldehyde	ST	45.4	89.5	128.5	143.1
		CO2	3.5	9.5	18.1	23.1
		CO	1.1	2.1	17.1	47.3
		Total	50.0	101.1	163.7	213.5
6	Iso butyraldehyde	ST	2.8	4.2	5.8	20.5
		IYT	8.8	11.4	22.2	16.3
		CO2	1.5	2.7	4.6	7.7
		CO	11.3	10.2	9.5	8.3
		Total	24.4	28.5	42.1	52.8
7	n-butyraldehyde	ST	3.1	2.7	5.5	20.5
		YT	6.2	11.4	23.9	41.7
		CO2	0.8	1.6	5.0	11.4
		CO	1.3	3.2	8.7	18.6
		Total	11.4	18.9	43.1	92.2
8	Propionaldehyde	ST	5.5	11.5	11.4	19.4
		PA	11.1	21.4	22.4	40.1
		CO2	2.2	3.8	5.4	9.1
		CO	4.6	10.1	13.2	27.4
		Total	23.4	46.8	52.4	96.0
9	ST	CO2	2.2	2.3	2.6	3.5
		CO	0.6	0.4	0.3	0.3

№	Oxidizing compounds	Oxidation products	Conversion rate of oxidation products at temperature T (K), ($w \cdot 10^{-2}$) mol/m ³ ·s			
			530	560	590	610
		Total	2.8	2.7	2.9	3.8
10	Propionic acid	CO ₂	1.4	2.5	4.1	5.7
		CO	-	0.3	2.5	4.8
		Total	1.4	2.8	6.6	10.5
11	n-butyric acid	CO ₂	1.3	1.6	2.9	4.4
		CO	0.2	0.5	1.4	4.4
		Total	1.5	2.1	4.3	8.8
12	isobutyric acid	CO ₂	0.6	1.1	2.1	4.5
		CO	-	0.5	1.3	4.7
		Total	0.6	1.6	3.4	9.2
13	AT	CO ₂	0.3	1.1	2.5	6.3
		CO	-	0.1	0.9	2.1
		Total	0.3	1.2	3.4	8.4
14	MAT	CO ₂	2.5	3.5	8.2	10.0
		CO	0.2	0.2	1.4	3.1
		Total	2.7	3.7	9.6	13.1

Figure 1 – Dependence of the conversion rates of aldehydes and acids on temperature during oxidation on the Mo₁₂PC_{s1.8}Pb_{o.5}CrO_x catalyst

According to Table 1:

1. Positions 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 correspond to acetaldehyde, isobutyraldehyde, propionaldehyde, n-butyraldehyde, and acetone.

2. Positions 6, 7, 8, 9 correspond to methacrolein (MA), ethylacrolein (EA), propylacrolein (PA), and acrolein (AKP).

3. Positions 10, 11, 12, 13, 14 correspond to methacrylic acid (MAK), propionic acid, isobutyric acid, n-butyric acid, and acetic acid.

In Table 1, the comparison of the oxidation rates of various aldehydes and acids is demonstrated. At 590 K, the oxidation rates of acrolein and acetic acid are nearly identical. However, among all the acids studied, acetic acid shows the highest stability.

The oxidation sequence of acids at 590 K is as follows:

Methacrylic acid → Propionic acid → n-Butyric acid → Isobutyric acid → Acrylic acid → Acetic acid

This sequence corresponds to the findings from the $\text{Mo}_{0.75}\text{V}_{20}\text{Te}_{0.5}\text{O}_x$ catalyst experiments.

Some aldehydes and acids exhibit temperature dependencies for their conversion rates, as shown in Figure 1. It is clear that unsaturated aldehydes have higher activation energies compared to saturated aldehydes and acetic acid. Among the acids, acetic acid has the highest activation energy.

Results and discussions: The results show that during methacrylic acid oxidation, the formation rates of CO and CO₂ are higher than during the oxidation of methacrolein. This suggests that the CO and CO₂ formed during methacrolein oxidation primarily result from the complete oxidation of methacrylic acid.

When comparing the oxidation rates of methacrolein and methacrylic acid, the rate of methacrylic acid formation from methacrolein is about three times higher than the rate of direct methacrylic acid oxidation. This demonstrates that methacrylic acid is mainly formed through the oxidation of methacrolein.

Acetic acid is mainly formed from aldehydes. However, it may also appear as an intermediate product in certain processes.

Further experiments (increasing the concentration of methacrolein while decreasing the temperature) confirmed that on the $\text{Mo}_{12}\text{P}_2\text{CS}_{1.8}\text{Pb}_{0.5}\text{CrO}_x$ catalyst, higher aldehydes and acids are not formed.

Acetone, acetaldehyde, and propionaldehyde are formed in very small quantities ($\leq 1.0\%$). This indicates that most of the acetic acid is directly formed from methacrolein oxidation.

Based on these observations, the following scheme for the methacrolein oxidation process is proposed:

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